

CHARACTERIZATION AND THERMAL EFFECT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOMATERIAL-REINFORCED-POLYPROPYLENE

A.D. Ngo, École de technologie supérieure, Canada

Objective and Materials

Talc comes from a mineral resource. So manufacturers are looking to replace Talc with another material that is lighter than Talc and a renewable resource.

Vegetable reinforcement

- Lighter
- Cheaper
- Are not harmful to manufacturing tools

Comparison: PP + Talc vs PP + Vegetable reinforcement

Mechanical Property

The processes manufacturing

Composition

62wt% Polypropylène (PP) + 5wt% Elastomer (POE) + 3wt% Compatibilizer (MAPP)

Matrix

Reinforcement

- F1: 30wt% Biochar
- F2: 30wt% Miscanthus
- F3: 15wt% Miscanthus + 15wt% Biochar

Density (g/cm³)

0,998 1,01 1,004 < 1,14

Mechanical Properties

Flexural properties of three biocomposites at 25°C, matrix material and commercial reference composite.

Tensile properties of three biocomposites at 25°C compared to that of the matrix and the PP/Talc commercial composite

Impact strength of A: PP/POE/MAPP; B: RTP 132 UV Talc/PP; C: F1; D: F2; E: F3

Thermal Effect

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Thermal effect on the mechanical properties of the studied biocomposites (a) Tensile modulus, (b) Tensile strength, (c) Flexural Modulus, (d) Flexural Strength